

Privacy Preservation in Textual Data: A Systematic Mapping Study on Differential Privacy and Semantic Similarity

Daniel Linhares Lim-Apo

¹University of Brasília (UnB), Department of Computer Science, Brasília, DF, Brazil
E-mail: daniel.unb@sede.com.br, ednacanedo@unb.br

Table 1. Privacy-preserving computational techniques for textual data analysis categorized by research cluster (RQ.2).

Cluster A: Transformer-Based LLMs	
Computational Approach or Concepts	Studies
BERT Model	[Stanik et al. 2021, Hu et al. 2024, Lit et al. 2022, Gambarelli et al. 2023, Yan et al. 2024]
BioBERT	[Hu et al. 2024]
Bio-NER	[Mehta et al. 2019]
BlueBERT	[Hu et al. 2024]
DeBERTa	[Gambarelli et al. 2023]
Language-agnostic BERT Sentence Embedding (LaBSE)	[Gambarelli et al. 2023]
Large Language Models (LLMs)	[Yan et al. 2024, Staufer et al. 2024, Gupta et al. 2024]
Large Scale Hierarchical Text Classification (LSHTC)	[Zhang et al. 2010]
Masked Language Model (MLM)	[Gambarelli et al. 2023]
RoBERTa	[Gambarelli et al. 2023]

Cluster B: Statistical and Sequence Models	
Computational Approach or Concepts	Studies
Conditional Random Fields (CRF)	[Mehta et al. 2019]
Hidden Markov Model (HMM)	[Mehta et al. 2019]
Logistic Regression (LR)	[Gambarelli et al. 2023]
Markov-models	[Saeed et al. 2020, Mehta et al. 2019, Nguyen et al. 2015]

Cluster C: Deep Neural Models	
Computational Approach or Concepts	Studies
BiLSTM network	[Languré and Zareei 2025, Hu et al. 2023]
Deep Learning	[Obeid et al. 2019]
Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)	[Meyer et al. 2023, Singhofer et al. 2021]
Model-Recurrent Neural Network (RNN)	[Feng et al. 2024]
Neural Network	[Abdalla et al. 2020]
Parallel Hybridization Approach (PHA)	[Al-Ghuribi et al. 2020]

Cluster D: Federated and Agent-Based Systems	
Computational Approach or Concepts	Studies
AI Agent	[Tang 2024]
FL-based gated recurrent unit neural network algorithm (Fed-GRU)	[Liu et al. 2020]
Hierarchical Federated Collaborative Computing (HFCC)	[Han et al. 2025]
Personalized Language Model Learning on Text Data Without User Identifiers	[Ding et al. 2025]
Multi-Agent	[Tang 2024]

Cluster E: Symbolic and Rule-Based Approaches	
Computational Approach or Concepts	Studies
Dictionary Creation	[Al-Ghuribi et al. 2020]
Double Propagation (DP)	[Al-Ghuribi et al. 2020]
Frequency-Based Approach (FBA)	[Al-Ghuribi et al. 2020]
Java StanfordCoreNLP	[Al-Ghuribi et al. 2020]
Knowledge Graphs (KGs)	[Joshi and Taherdoost 2025]
SPARQL	[Nethravathi et al. 2016]

Cluster F: Formal Anonymization Techniques	
Computational Approach or Concepts	Studies
Improved Scalable k-Anonymization (ImSKA)	[Mehta et al. 2019]
Scalable k-Anonymization (SKA) using MapReduce	[Mehta et al. 2019]

Cluster G: General NLP and NER	
Computational Approach or Concepts	Studies
Natural Language Processing (NLP)	[Hu et al. 2021, Fursov et al. 2022, Ismail and Rahman 2014, Agarwal et al. 2021, Osman and Barukub 2020, Gupta and Patel 2021, Sultana Ritu et al. 2018, enel et al. 2018, Zhu et al. 2021, Zaware et al. 2021, P. and Shaji 2019, Hu et al. 2024, Lit et al. 2022, Mcconkey and Olukoya 2024, Vats et al. 2024, Fei et al. 2024, Joshi and Taherdoost 2025, Singhofer et al. 2021, Gupta et al. 2024, Abdalla et al. 2020, van Baal et al. 2025]
NER	[Mehta et al. 2019]

Tools	
	Studies
ChatGPT	[Yan et al. 2024, van Staalduine and Zuiderwijk 2025, Gupta et al. 2024]
SPaCy	[Gambarelli et al. 2023]
Tensorflow	[Sultana Ritu et al. 2018]

References

- Abdalla, M., Abdalla, M., Hirst, G., and Rudzicz, F. (2020). Exploring the Privacy-Preserving Properties of Word Embeddings: Algorithmic Validation Study. *JOURNAL OF MEDICAL INTERNET RESEARCH*, 22(7). Place: 130 QUEENS QUAY E, STE 1102, TORONTO, ON M5A 0P6, CANADA Publisher: JMIR PUBLICATIONS, INC Type: Article.
- Agarwal, M., Kalia, R., Bahel, V., and Thomas, A. (2021). AutoEval: A NLP Approach for Automatic Test Evaluation System. In *2021 IEEE 4th International Conference on Computing, Power and Communication Technologies (GUCON)*, pages 1–6.
- Al-Ghuribi, S. M., Mohd Noah, S. A., and Tiun, S. (2020). Unsupervised Semantic Approach of Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis for Large-Scale User Reviews. *IEEE Access*, 8:218592–218613.
- Ding, Y., Tan, Y., Liu, X., Niu, C., Meng, F., Zhou, J., Liu, N., Wu, F., and Chen, G. (2025). Personalized Language Model Learning on Text Data Without User Identifiers. In *Proceedings of the 31st ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining V.1*, KDD '25, pages 224–235, New York, NY, USA. Association for Computing Machinery.

- Fei, X., Chai, S., He, W., Dai, L., Xu, R., and Cai, L. (2024). A Systematic Study on the Privacy Protection Mechanism of Natural Language Processing in Medical Health Records. In *2024 IEEE 2nd International Conference on Sensors, Electronics and Computer Engineering (ICSECE)*, pages 1819–1824.
- Feng, J., Yang, L. T., Ren, B., Zou, D., Dong, M., and Zhang, S. (2024). Tensor Recurrent Neural Network With Differential Privacy. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 73(3):683–693.
- Fursov, I., Zaytsev, A., Burnyshev, P., Dmitrieva, E., Klyuchnikov, N., Kravchenko, A., Artemova, E., Komleva, E., and Burnaev, E. (2022). A Differentiable Language Model Adversarial Attack on Text Classifiers. *IEEE Access*, 10:17966–17976.
- Gambarelli, G., Gangemi, A., and Tripodi, R. (2023). Is Your Model Sensitive? SPEDAC: A New Resource for the Automatic Classification of Sensitive Personal Data. *IEEE Access*, 11:10864–10880.
- Gupta, B. B., Gaurav, A., Arya, V., Alhalabi, W., Alsalman, D., and Vijayakumar, P. (2024). Enhancing user prompt confidentiality in Large Language Models through advanced differential encryption. *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, 116:109215.
- Gupta, H. and Patel, M. (2021). Method Of Text Summarization Using Lsa And Sentence Based Topic Modelling With Bert. In *2021 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Smart Systems (ICAIS)*, pages 511–517.
- Han, C., Yang, T., Cui, Z., and Sun, X. (2025). A Privacy-Preserving and Trustworthy Inference Framework for LLM-IoT Integration via Hierarchical Federated Collaborative Computing. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, pages 1–1.
- Hu, J., Bao, R., Lin, Y., Zhang, H., and Xiang, Y. (2024). Accurate Medical Named Entity Recognition Through Specialized NLP Models. In *2024 6th International Conference on Frontier Technologies of Information and Computer (ICFTIC)*, pages 578–582.
- Hu, X., Zhang, H., and Sun, Y. (2023). Chinese Medical Short Text Matching Model Based on Fine-Tuning BERT-Attention-BiLSTM. In *2023 IEEE/ACIS 23rd International Conference on Computer and Information Science (ICIS)*, pages 91–96.
- Hu, Y., Wang, H., Ji, T., Xiao, X., Luo, X., Gao, P., and Guo, Y. (2021). CHAMP: Characterizing Undesired App Behaviors from User Comments Based on Market Policies. In *2021 IEEE/ACM 43rd International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, pages 933–945. ISSN: 1558-1225.
- Ismail, S. and Rahman, M. S. (2014). Bangla word clustering based on N-gram language model. In *2014 International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Information & Communication Technology*, pages 1–5.
- Joshi, H. S. and Taherdoost, H. (2025). Ethics in Natural Language Processing: Addressing Bias, Privacy, and Misinformation. In *2025 International Conference on Pervasive Computational Technologies (ICPCT)*, pages 359–364.
- Langur, A. d. L. and Zareei, M. (2025). Privacy-Preserving Emotion Detection: Evaluating the Trade-Off Between K-Anonymity and Model Performance. *IEEE Access*, 13:105901–105910.

- Lit, Z., Sit, S., Wang, J., and Xiao, J. (2022). Federated Split BERT for Heterogeneous Text Classification. In *2022 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, pages 1–8. ISSN: 2161-4407.
- Liu, Y., Yu, J. J. Q., Kang, J., Niyato, D., and Zhang, S. (2020). Privacy-Preserving Traffic Flow Prediction: A Federated Learning Approach. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 7(8):7751–7763.
- Mcconkey, R. and Olukoya, O. (2024). Runtime and Design Time Completeness Checking of Dangerous Android App Permissions Against GDPR. *IEEE Access*, 12:1–22.
- Mehta, B., Rao, U. P., Gupta, R., and Conti, M. (2019). Towards privacy preserving unstructured big data publishing. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 36(4):3471–3482. Publisher: SAGE Publications.
- Meyer, S., Tilli, P., Denisov, P., Lux, F., Koch, J., and Vu, N. T. (2023). Anonymizing Speech with Generative Adversarial Networks to Preserve Speaker Privacy. In *2022 IEEE Spoken Language Technology Workshop (SLT)*, pages 912–919.
- Nethravathi, N. P., Rao, P. G., Desai, V. J., Shenoy, P. D., Venugopal, K. R., and Indiramma, M. (2016). SWCTE: Semantic weighted context tagging engine for privacy preserving data mining. In *2016 International Conference on Data Science and Engineering (ICDSE)*, pages 1–5.
- Nguyen, N. T. H., Miwa, M., Tsuruoka, Y., and Tojo, S. (2015). Identifying synonymy between relational phrases using word embeddings. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 56:94–102.
- Obeid, J. S., Heider, P. M., Weeda, E. R., Matuskowitz, A. J., Carr, C. M., Gagnon, K., Crawford, T., and Meystre, S. M. (2019). Impact of De-Identification on Clinical Text Classification Using Traditional and Deep Learning Classifiers. In Ohno-Machado, L. and Seroussi, B., editors, *MEDINFO 2019: HEALTH AND WELLBEING E-NETWORKS FOR ALL*, volume 264 of *Studies in Health Technology and Informatics*, pages 283–287, NIEUWE HEMWEG 6B, 1013 BG AMSTERDAM, NETHERLANDS. IOS PRESS. Backup Publisher: French Assoc Med Informat ISSN: 0926-9630 Type: Proceedings Paper.
- Osman, A. H. and Barukub, O. M. (2020). Graph-Based Text Representation and Matching: A Review of the State of the Art and Future Challenges. *IEEE Access*, 8:87562–87583.
- P., S. and Shaji, A. P. (2019). A Survey on Semantic Similarity. In *2019 International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication and Control (ICAC3)*, pages 1–8.
- Saeed, M. Y., Awais, M., Talib, R., and Younas, M. (2020). Unstructured Text Documents Summarization With Multi-Stage Clustering. *IEEE Access*, 8:212838–212854.
- Singhofer, F., Garifullina, A., Kern, M., and Scherp, A. (2021). A novel approach on the joint de-identification of textual and relational data with a modified mondrian algorithm. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM Symposium on Document Engineering, DocEng '21*, pages 1–10, New York, NY, USA. Association for Computing Machinery.

- Stanik, C., Pietz, T., and Maalej, W. (2021). Unsupervised Topic Discovery in User Comments. In *2021 IEEE 29th International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)*, pages 150–161. ISSN: 2332-6441.
- Staufer, D., Pallas, F., and Berendt, B. (2024). Silencing the Risk, Not the Whistle: A Semi-automated Text Sanitization Tool for Mitigating the Risk of Whistleblower Re-Identification. In *Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency, FAccT '24*, pages 733–745, New York, NY, USA. Association for Computing Machinery.
- Sultana Ritu, Z., Nowshin, N., Mahadi Hasan Nahid, M., and Ismail, S. (2018). Performance Analysis of Different Word Embedding Models on Bangla Language. In *2018 International Conference on Bangla Speech and Language Processing (ICBSLP)*, pages 1–5.
- Tang, H. (2024). Study on Multi-Agent Interactive Learning Models Oriented Towards Dynamic Interactive Topologies. In *2024 IEEE 7th International Conference on Automation, Electronics and Electrical Engineering (AUTEEE)*, pages 271–275. ISSN: 2831-4549.
- van Baal, S. T., Bogdanski, P., Daryanani, A., Walasek, L., and Newall, P. (2025). The lived experience of gambling-related harm in natural language. *Psychology of Addictive Behaviors*, 39(4):397–409. Place: US Publisher: American Psychological Association.
- van Staalduine, N. and Zuiderwijk, A. (2025). Exploring the Viability of ChatGPT for Personal Data Anonymization in Government: A Comprehensive Analysis of Possibilities, Risks, and Ethical Implications. *Digit. Gov.: Res. Pract.*, 6(2). Place: New York, NY, USA Publisher: Association for Computing Machinery.
- Vats, A., Liu, Z., Su, P., Paul, D., Ma, Y., Pang, Y., Ahmed, Z., and Kalinli, O. (2024). Recovering from Privacy-Preserving Masking with Large Language Models. In *ICASSP 2024 - 2024 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 10771–10775. ISSN: 2379-190X.
- Yan, B., Li, K., Xu, M., Dong, Y., Zhang, Y., Ren, Z., and Cheng, X. (2024). On Protecting the Data Privacy of Large Language Models (LLMs): A Survey. In *2024 International Conference on Meta Computing (ICMC)*, pages 1–12.
- Zaware, S., Patadiya, D., Gaikwad, A., Gulhane, S., and Thakare, A. (2021). Text Summarization using TF-IDF and Textrank algorithm. In *2021 5th International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI)*, pages 1399–1407.
- Zhang, J., Zhao, H., and Lu, B.-L. (2010). A comparative study on two large-scale hierarchical text classification tasks' solutions. In *2010 International Conference on Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, volume 6, pages 3275–3280. ISSN: 2160-1348.
- Zhu, L., Li, W., Shi, Y., and Guo, K. (2021). SentiVec: Learning Sentiment-Context Vector via Kernel Optimization Function for Sentiment Analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 32(6):2561–2572.
- enel, L. K., Utlu, ., Yücesoy, V., Koç, A., and Çukur, T. (2018). Semantic Structure and Interpretability of Word Embeddings. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 26(10):1769–1779.